

INVESTIGATION OF GROUNDNUT SHELL AS A COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties of groundnut shell were investigated based on varying volume of shell and Urea formaldehyde. Tensile and compressive composite samples were produced from aluminium mould. The material used for the work were dried grinded groundnut shell, Urea formaldehyde (uf), digital weighing scale, mould material, metallic sieve, electric oven and lubricating oil. Several proportions by volume of shell and Urea formaldehyde was tested which gave yield strength of 41.56mpa, 46.35mpa; 39.27mpa, 43.20mpa; 41.14mpa, 49.08mpa; 35.22mpa, 40.21mpa; 29.93mpa, 35.09mpa with a compressive strength of 89.27mpa, 94.37mpa; 72.38mpa, 82.51mpa; 80.65mpa, 92.51mpa; 64.34mpa, 74.22mpa; 59.48mpa, 68.64mpa, was achieved. An established value of 12% volume of shell plus 79g of urea formaldehyde in the sample gave the best or optimum composite material for application as a particle board or roofing material. Beyond the established value, the strength of sample begins to diminish. It can therefore be inferred that, groundnut shell can be use for low strength application in the building industry most likely as a particle board, roofing sheet and panel board. This material is, light in weight, and resistant to corrosion. The addition of fillers to the shell, e.g. Wood dust or calcium carbonate would improve the composite adhesion; likewise reduction of high grams of Urea in the solution to appropriate ratio may improve adhesion greatly, hence increasing the strength of the composite.

INTRODUCTION

There are many situations in engineering where no single material will be suitable to meet a particular requirement. However, two or more materials in combination may possess the desired properties and provide a feasible solution to the material selection problem.

Composite materials can refer to any multi-phase material; it is usually restricted to "tailored made" material in which two or more constituent materials that remain separate and distinct on a macroscopic level while forming a single component (Veron, 1992).

Nanocomposites are materials that are created by introducing nano-particulate into a macroscopic sample material. The nanomaterial tends to drastically add to the electrical, thermal and mechanical properties of the original material.

There are two categories of constituent materials matrix and reinforcement. At least one portion (fraction) of each type is required. The matrix material by and supports the reinforcement materials by maintaining their relative position. The reinforcement impart special physical (mechanical and electrical) properties to enhance the matrix properties. Engineering composite materials must be formed to shape. This involves strategically placing the reinforcement while manipulating the matrix properties to achieve a melding event at or near the beginning of the component life cycle.

Many commercially produced composite use a polymer matrix material often called a resin or resin solution. There are many different polymers available depending upon the starting raw ingredients. There are several broad categories each with numerous variation. The most common categories are known as polymers, polyester, formaldehyde (pf), Urea formaldehyde (uf) and others. These matrix is often a resin that binds the fibre together, giving the material its tensile strength, transferring load from broken fibre to unbroken ones and between fibres that are not oriented along lines of tension. Also, unless the matrix chosen is especially flexible, it presents the fibre from

Table 1: CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF GROUNDNUT SHELL

Constituents	Cellulose	Carbohydrate	Protein	Minerals	Lipids
Percentage (%)	65.5	21.2	7.3	4.5	1.2

(Reddy, 1998)

buckling in compression. Some composite use an aggregate instead of, or in addition to fibres. In terms of stress, any fibre serves to resist tension, the matrix serves to resist shear and all material present serves to resist compression. Composite materials are divided into two main categories; short fibre reinforced materials and Continuous fibre reinforcement materials. (Wikipedia Com., 2006).

This paper is aimed at producing a composite material using groundnut shell for low strength use suitable for practical engineering application. This is done by the determination and comparison of the tensile and compressive strength of the groundnut fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composite based on the variation in proportions by volume of the groundnut shell fibre to that of a matrix material reinforcement agent.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Groundnut botanically belongs to *Arachis hypogaea* Linn of leguminous family. Groundnut is self-pollinated; annual, herbaceous legume crop. A complete seed of groundnut is called pod and contains one to five kermils which develops underground in a needlelike structure called peg which grow into the soil and then converts into a pod. Groundnut has taproot system which has many nodules, present in root and lateral roots. These nodulus contains *Rhizobium* bacterial, which are symbiotic in nature and focus atmosphere nitrogen. Outer layer of groundnut is called groundnut shell: The shell constitute about 25-35% of the pod. The seed accounts for the remaining portion (65-75%). The colour of the testa varies from red, brown, purple to white depending on the type. The kermel and germ are normally white in colour.

There are four botanical types of groundnut namely Valencica bunch, Spanish bunch, Virginia runner and Virginia bunch. They differ in their chemical composition and oil quality.

Virginia bunch type seed are richer in oil and chemical content followed by Spanish bunch; Valenia protein content is higher, Virginia runner have higher soluble sugar while Valenia type has highest oleic acid.

In general, it can be stated that Virginia runner types have better chemical composition with balanced oil quality. (Graham *et al*, 2002).

Various means of shelling groundnut pod to obtain the husk have been in practice. These include both mechanised method and traditional methods despite it's tediousness; these include pounding in motar with pestle, beating with stick on a flat surface and cracking with a stone on top of another stone or hard flat surface. (Atiku, et-al 2004)

Over the years, mechanical method of shelling have been developed to solve the difficulties associated with shelling groundnut.

It has been reported that south America was the place from where cultivation of groundnut originated and spread into Brazil, southern Bolivia and North-western Argentina. Groundnut was introduced by the Portuguese from Brazil to west Africa and then to south-western in the 16th century (Pandey, 1998).

Though different types of groundnut differ in chemical composition and colour, groundnut shell of different types of groundnut does not differ in any aspect, the chemical composition, colour, strength, and general properties of the different types are the same. (Akobundu, 1987)

Over the years, groundnut shell constitute of the common solid waste especially in the developing part of this world. It's potential as a useful engineering material has not been investigated despite the fact that various resins that could be used as addition are available. Presently, resins are used in the production of particle board and woody composite.

Resins for particle board and woody composite include urea formaldehyde (uf), phenol formaldehyde (pf) and to a much lesser extent melamine formaldehyde (mf). The type and amount of resins used for particle board depend on

TABLE 2: Various proportion of shell, Urea formaldehyde and strength of sample.

S/N o	Shell Vol fraction (%)	Uf Volume fraction (g)	Failure force tensile test (KN)	Yield strength (mpa)	failure force compression (KN)	Compressive strength (mpa)
1	6	74	5.37	41.556	5.40	89.270
2	6	79	5.99	46.354	6.01	94.370
3	8	74	4.10	39.271	3.89	72.381
4	8	79	4.51	43.201	3.14	82.514
5	10	74	4.15	41.140	3.04	80.647
6	10	79	5.93	49.081	4.20	92.506
7.	12	74	4.65	35.223	2.84	64.342
8.	12	79	4.22	40.214	2.95	74.224
9	14	74	3.74	29.927	2.13	59.482
10	14	79	3.85	35.088	2.20	68.639

the type of product desired. Based on the weight of dry resins, solids and Oven dry product weight of the particle resin content is usually in the range of 4 to 5% but most likely 6 to 9% resins are usually introduced in water solution containing about 50 to 60% solids. Beside resins, paraffin wax emulsion is added to improve moisture resistance. The amount of wax ranges from 0.3 – 1% based on the Oven dry weight of the particle diameter. (Maloney, 1989).

For the purpose of producing a composite material/product, uniformity, consistency and predictability are accomplished by the reduction of the separated portions of plants into small relatively uniform and consistent particle or fibre where effect of different will average out. Size reduction is sometimes augmented by chemical treatment designed to weaken the bounds between the component. (Brent and Chow, 1994)

Melamine formaldehyde resins are used as moulding powder and for the manufacture of laminate adhesive and binders for shell moulding. (Ibhadode, 2001).

Urea Formaldehyde (uf) is made by condensation reaction between Urea and formaldehyde. It's powder is prepared in a similar way to phenol formaldehyde. The resins are light in colour such that pigment may be added to give a wide range of colour. It gives hard and rigid material. It has good resistance to most chemical. These resins are used in the manufacture of laminate as adhesive and binders.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

The materials and equipment employed in this study are dried grinded groundnut shell. Maloney, 1989 established that for a composite testing, the sample range should be from 0.2 – 0.4mm in thickness, 3.0 – 30mm in which and 10.0 – 60.0mm length. Urea formaldehyde (uf), digital weighing scale with it's measuring capacity range from 0 – 100 grams, mould material made of pure aluminium, metallic sieve, electric oven, lubricating oil and Graduated Beaker.

Methodology

The strength of the composite largely depends on the preparation of the shell. The shell are collected and Sun dried, hammer milled to reduce it's size to smaller ones and then grinded in a grinding machine and sieved to obtain a fine uniform shape and size.

The mould was constructed solely for producing the composite material. The material selected for fabrication is aluminium due to its availability, relatively low cost and resistance to corrosion. The design and construction was carried out with technical consideration to enhance precision and accuracy in mould cavity dimensioning.

The aluminium mould was fabricated from sand casting process; and was further machined for acceptable surface finish on which the composite finish depends on. The mould consist of a cope/male and a drag/female, each with semi-circular groove, symmetrical when put together.

Plate 1: Fabricated Aluminium Mould

Plate 2: Sample Specimen

The groundnut shell and resin were mixed in varying proportions as seen in table 1. The mixed sample is then compressed into the produced mould properly. Compression is done carefully to avoid build up of air gap within the sample. The cope is then opened and sample is carefully removed from mould and sun dried for 8hrs in a solar temperature of 38°C.

Result analysis and calculation

The strength and modulus of a composite having aligned fibre are dependent on the direction in which they are measured (anisotropic). These properties are demonstrated mathematically by an isostrain model known as the law of mixture. This law applies for determining the modulus of elasticity of a continuous and aligned fibrous composite in the longitudinal direction. It is expressed as

$$E_c = E_m V_n + E_f V_f \dots\dots\dots(1) \quad (Callister,1997)$$

Where E = Elastic modulus and V = Volume fracture

Subscripts c, m, and f represent composite, matrix and fibre respectively. Since the composite consist of only matrix and fibre phase, i.e

$$V_m + V_f = 1 \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Therefore eqn (1) becomes.

$$E_c = E_m [1 - V_f] + [E_f V_f] \dots\dots\dots 3 \quad (Callister,1997)$$

The internal bond strength (dry/wet) is 1.3 – 1.4 N/mm² for bamboo mat sheet (sample subjected to 3 hrs boiling is dried to 12% moisture content and tested and load heaving capacity for the same bamboo mat sheet is 4.8N/mm of width (Span length 1000mm) (bmtpc.org,2006).

Further more, the thickness of fibber glass roofing sheet is 1.1mm and has tensile strength of 1120kg/cm² and compressive test of 69kg/cm² (mamata.com;2006).

Toughness and Fibre Pullout

Toughness is a measure of amount of energy absorbed by a material as it fractures; the total area which the material tensile stress-strain curves indicates toughness. This property does not involve in linear combination of toughness of individual constituent of composite material as demonstrated by the law of mixture although application in determining the toughness of the composite material is described as

$$G_e = V + G_{e^*} [1 - V_f] G_{e^m} \dots\dots\dots 4$$

This does not hold always as explained by Ashby and Jones 1997.

Establishing the relevant equation to be employed for determining the proportion of constituent in composite sample;

From Archimedes principle:

$$M_i = \rho_i V_i \dots\dots\dots 5$$

and $V_f = V_i / V_T \dots\dots\dots 6$ Or $V_i = V_f V_T$
(Callister, 1997)

The total volume of the mould cavity V_f is constant.

$$V_T = V_{uf} + V_o$$

where m = mass, ρ = density, V = volume and V_f = volume fraction

Subscript i, o, U_f , and T denote constituents shell, Urea formaldehyde and total respectfully.

Substituting equation (6) into (5) we have

$$m_i = \rho_i V_f V_i \dots\dots\dots 7$$

Volume of mould cavity (V_T)

$$V_T = \frac{\pi d^2 L}{4} \dots\dots\dots 8$$

therefore $\frac{\pi x (827 - 12) x 15.5}{4} = 156.152 \text{mm}^2$

Area of mould cavity (A)

$$A = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \dots\dots\dots 9 \quad \text{(Callister; 1997)}$$

Therefore, $A = \frac{(12.827)^2 \times \pi}{4} = 129.223 \text{mm}^2$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

$$\text{Yield Strength (Tensile)} = F = \frac{\text{Failure force (KN)}}{A \text{ (mm}^2\text{)}}$$

(Density $P_{uf} = 0.9\text{gkm}^2$) (Ababio; 1995)

and Area = $\pi d^2/4$ (Callister, 1997)

Where $d = 12.827\text{mm}$

Therefore $A = \frac{(12.827)^2}{4} \times \pi = 129.2\text{mm}^2$

$$\text{Compressive Strength (Compression)} = \frac{\text{Failure force (KN)}}{\text{Area (mm}^2\text{)}}$$

and Area = $L \times B$ (Callister, 1997)

where $L = 3.175$ and $B = 19.05$
 $A = 3.175 \times 19.05 = 60.484\text{mm}^2$

The table below indicates the improving strength of groundnut shell composite due to varying proportion of both shell, and Urea formaldehyde content.

Table 2 shows the various proportions of shell and Urea formaldehyde used.

From the result of this study as presented in table 1, it was observed that groundnut shell composite is not as strong in tensile strength as it is in compressive strength due to or because of its brittle nature. Furthermore it was also observed that increasing the volume of the shell further increase the strength of the composite. As seen in table 1, the more the volume of urea formaldehyde in the sample, the greater its strength. An established volume of 12% volume of shell plus 79g of urea formaldehyde in the sample gives the best or optimum composite material for application as a particle board or roofing material. Beyond the established value, the strength as observed, begins to diminish

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The mechanical properties of groundnut shell composite were investigated based on varying proportion of shell and Urea formaldehyde. Composite and compressive sample was produced from aluminium mould, several proportion by volume of shell and Urea formaldehyde were used and an established volume of 12% volume of shell plus 79g of urea formaldehyde in the sample gives the best or optimum composite material. Various steps were taken to achieve these composite, they include drying grinding, weighting, mixing oven drying (Heating) and testing (Tensile and compressive strength test).

This investigation has shown that groundnut shell can be employed as composite material for low strength application. The relatively low strength of groundnut shell composite should not be seen in negative perspective, because there are several non-structural application where the strength properties of groundnut composite would meet the technical and product requirement, particularly where the competitive price level, light weight, flexibility, non – degradability and corrosion resistance of groundnut shell composite is taken into consideration. Some application of this kind of material can be in the production of particle board, roofing sheet e.t.c.

Groundnut shell composite can be used but certain critical issues should still be needed to address and resolved concerning.

- i) The addition of fillers to the shell e.g. wood dust or calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) to improve the composite adhesion.
- ii) Reduction of high level or grams of Urea in the solution or composite. This is because high level Urea in the composite reduces adhesion and strength of the composite greatly.

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